

INNOVATIVE EXPERIENCE IN THE FORMATION OF CREATIVE AND SPIRITUAL COMPETENCIES OF PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This research paper presents the current state of improving pedagogical skills and preparing a teacher for practical aspects in the system of moral education of a student, characterized by the presence of significant theoretical gaps.

I. Introduction.

One of the primary tasks that are currently most relevant in the system of continuous pedagogical education, theorists and practitioners call the inclusion of issues of moral education in the system of improving the pedagogical skills of teachers. The existing problems of modern society make it necessary to educate a citizen with a new way of thinking and worldview, with a high moral culture. Moral position, knowledge of the laws of morality and ethical standards are an important component of a comprehensively developed personality, which is the ultimate goal of the modern educational process. A special place in the system of moral education is occupied by primary school, where, following the educational processes that take place during preschool education, the foundations of moral and ethical knowledge and ideas are purposefully laid. The coming third millennium is characterized by the advent of a new era, which implies the need for the individual to build a new system of relations with society and the surrounding reality. These realities of modern times make it necessary to think about the moral components of human relationships, which are an important component of a comprehensively developed personality. Moral education in the context of changes in modern society ceases to be a problem of the educational system or family education.

These issues become significant at the state level, in accordance with which they require a detailed development of forms, methods, and approaches [1-3]. The teacher, who implements the tasks of moral education, needs to personally correspond to the ideas about the moral personality that exists in our society. Knowledge of the moral foundations, rules of ethics and morality is not always sufficient in the system of educational work in matters of moral education [4].

Understanding the importance of a personal example in pedagogical activity, the teacher himself must comply with these rules, adhere to the rules of ethics and morality in his own

actions and in relation to students and other people. This correspondence requires the teacher to have a conscious approach to their own professional activities and a constant desire for self-improvement in professional and personal terms.

II. Methods of research

Educator in the modern sense is a professional, of a high level, with a sufficient amount of scientific knowledge, able to take on non-standard situations, implement creative projects, be ready for self-education, and understand high civic responsibility for the results of professional activities. Realizing the high level of social responsibility of their professional activities, the teacher needs to constantly develop and improve himself. Also in modern conditions we are talking about the need to show creativity in pedagogical activity in order to educate a free, independent, active person. Many theorists and practicing teachers pay enough attention to this component of pedagogical activity, without which it is impossible to talk about the level of professionalism that modern realities impose on a representative of the teaching profession [5-6].

Considering the activity of a teacher, from the point of view of its creative component, it is necessary to note the importance of this component in the complex of professional competencies, especially for a primary school teacher.

It is also necessary to note the importance of interpersonal relationships between the teacher and the student. In the process of building these relationships at the elementary school stage, the leading role belongs to the teacher, as a psychologically significant person for the child. In the process of building personal relationships with each student, an elementary school teacher must adhere to moral standards and comply with them, representing an example for his students. The teacher should treat his students from the standpoint of partnerships, in the context of democratic changes in our society. In accordance with what, at this stage, the issues of pedagogical skill of the teacher are considered relevant, these issues require detailed consideration, updating in accordance with the modern realities of the teaching profession, with the new social requirements of society. The profession of a teacher is one of the most creative professions that require constant personal self-improvement, the search for new solutions, and the results of pedagogical activity do not always appear immediately.

The practical activity of teachers, its analysis shows that a practicing teacher is not always ready to work in conditions that require the adoption of an optimal pedagogical decision in a particular pedagogical situation. Often a practicing teacher is not able to make independent serious decisions, this skill requires serious practice and theoretical knowledge. The independence of the teacher in the design of the educational process requires a fairly large amount of theoretical knowledge, which can be provided by a higher educational institution and practical activities, however, this skill is to some extent formed for quite a long time. In practice, there are cases when a young specialist who is fluent in theory found it difficult to make independent decisions on a particular issue that constantly arises in the course of his professional activity, and in the absence of this skill from a teacher, we can talk about possible gaps in the educational process. In this situation, the process of developing pedagogical skills in the best way also ensures the development of the creative component and the ability to self-reflection of one's own professional activity.

The formation and development of the system of pedagogical excellence is based on the foundations of the advanced development of pedagogical education.

Fig. 1. The relationship of motivation with the nature of learning activities and behavior

Researches of scientists show that often the professional activity of many teachers is full of stereotypes and methodical clichés, which makes it impossible to develop the personality of a teacher as a professional, does not stimulate, but hinders his creative potential. In accordance with this, these scientists speak of the need for systematic special work on the formation and development of future teachers' motivation to improve their own pedagogical skills.

It is worth noting a number of main factors that determine the modern development of the educational process and indicate the need to form and develop in future teachers the desire to improve pedagogical skills.

Firstly, at this stage of the development of society, a special model of education becomes relevant, which basically has the creative initiative of a practicing teacher, his independence and competitiveness, the ability to act in non-standard situations, quickly make independent decisions that ensure the optimality of the educational process. It is worth noting the dependence of the teacher's creative potential on the level of formation of his professional thinking. The level of formation of the professional thinking of the teacher allows the teacher to apply innovative methods in his work, to be active in the professional sense, contributes to the active reflection of his own professional activity, which generally increases the professional level of the specialist and makes him competitive. Pedagogical activity is a process in which the teacher has the opportunity to show the full range of their creative abilities. Speaking about the possibilities of these manifestations, it is worth correlating the activity of a teacher with a constant creative search, without which it is impossible to imagine a developing teacher striving for excellence, representing a vivid example for his students to follow.

Secondly, the theoretical level of knowledge in academic disciplines has increased

significantly, this process has contributed to an increase in the contradictions between the overall goal of the educational process and the capabilities that future teachers have, as well as their ability to adequately solve practical problems that arise in the process of educational activities.

Thirdly, it is worth noting the emergence of serious changes in the education system. In this case, we mean the processes of diversification, the presence in school practice of new educational technologies and forms of education, as well as the opportunity for the teaching staff of an educational institution to choose the educational and methodological base themselves. At the same time, often young teachers who have a sufficient amount of theoretical knowledge obtained within the framework of the system of higher psychological and pedagogical education cannot use the skills of making independent decisions in practice, since this skill requires some experience. At the same time, there are cases when novice teachers lack theoretical knowledge, as well as practical skills, in the process of organizing educational activities. It also requires some practice in the ability to show creative qualities in the process of professional activity. The above examples make it difficult to improve the pedagogical skills of a novice teacher, his self-education.

III. Results

The importance of the presence of these skills in the teacher is due to the need to form students' leading competencies and abilities to carry out independent cognitive activity.

These processes contribute to the improvement of professional competencies throughout the entire professional activity. In such a case, it is the mobilization of the knowledge acquired and replenished by the teacher and the skills being formed, which contributes to the solution of emerging problem situations. A teacher with these abilities is able to make the necessary professional decisions and can form the student's subjective position.

Researchers have proved the direct dependence of the teacher's skill on how much he is able to show his creative potential, professional intuition, inspiration, which in general constitute the so-called "pedagogical talent". One of the necessary conditions for improving the skills of a teacher is his pedagogical activity, which must be constantly improved. In this process, an important role is assigned to the so-called environment, that is, the teaching staff of an educational institution, its microclimate, existing pedagogical traditions, the mentoring system, the nature of personal relationships between team members and management, as well as teachers with each other.

IV. Conclusion.

The studied problem allows us to determine the vector of possible directions for further research work. Promising areas for studying the issues of improving the pedagogical skills of teachers in the context of moral education can be the training in institutions of additional professional education of school leaders (in particular, deputy directors for educational work in elementary school), teachers of additional education, improvement of training technologies, retraining in the system improving pedagogical skills and the use of new innovative technologies; studying the features of the formation of teacher skills necessary in matters of moral education, located in different educational environments (university - school - a system

for improving pedagogical skills); further development of educational and methodological materials on this issue.

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